

THE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES

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Abstract. *This article emphasizes that the use of modern technologies is an important factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of natural sciences. Opinions were expressed that classes based on multimedia tools increase the effectiveness of learning, consolidate knowledge, and freely use them in practice to form skills and qualifications.*

Keywords: *multimedia, innovation, animation, digital educational resource, audio, communication, graphics, video, competence.*

INTRODUCTION

The experience of using multimedia tools in the process of national education in Uzbekistan is being formed. Because it is also a need of time. Today, the effective use of modern computer and information technologies is considered the main factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of natural science. The use of "multimedia lessons" makes it possible to improve the quality and efficiency of the teaching process in physics and chemistry.

Multimedia, or digital learning resources, help students to work better with mental images using various multimedia elements that support information processing. Research on the use of multimedia in education shows that students who combine images and words have more positive results than those who use the words only [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

From a pedagogical point of view, multimedia tools represent a new computer approach to the educational process of younger schoolchildren. Thus, it is an important tool for improving the efficiency of the educational process among students. For this reason, it is recommended to use "Multimedia lesson", "Slide lesson", "visual lesson", which represent the main aspects of pedagogical technologies developed during the study of elementary school lessons. A seminar lesson is a lesson that gathers students' independent presentations and creates a basis for discussion when necessary. In such classes, the teacher acts as a guide, and students participate in educational activities as independent, creative individuals with their own opinions.

Currently, a comprehensive study of the effectiveness of any educational discipline of general secondary education in its entirety or in what part of it is carried out using ICT, or the pedagogical principles of the application of ICT, its psychological characteristics, the mechanism and factors of its influence on the process of cognition, as well as many other aspects is becoming relevant. This creates the basis for the formation of a new content and essence in the educational system, in particular in the organization and implementation of educational processes, the development of educational and methodological support, especially in increasing the efficiency of passing and mastering training. In the successful implementation of such a huge task, it is of particular importance to convey to the teacher and students the necessary educational literature in the state language. The methodological instruction is intended for teachers operating in secondary schools, which includes knowledge of the formation of a new content and essence in the educational system, in particular, in the organization and implementation of educational processes, the development of educational and methodological support, especially in increasing the efficiency

of passing and mastering training sessions. The main goal of all reforms in the field of education is to educate spiritually perfectly developed people, improve the educational system, carry out lesson processes on the basis of new pedagogical and information technologies in accordance with the requirements of the All-Round time. That is why today special attention is paid to the effective use of modern technologies of computer and information technology in the educational system. And this is due to the fact that in the process of education, pedagogical personnel who provide students with knowledge in various disciplines can use modern means of information technology, first of all, to increase the level of knowledge and qualifications in this area, technical support of the educational system, and create full opportunities for using the internet, an effective result can be achieved. One of the main ways to improve the quality and effectiveness of the educational system will be the use of modern Information Communication Technologies in the educational process, including multimedia training courses, ensuring interactive activity of the teacher and the student, attracting highly qualified personnel in the development of multimedia training courses and textbooks. Multimedia creates opportunities to describe information in different ways and create dynamic images, perceive and visualize it through the organs of vision and hearing.

In multimedia technologies, information is expressed in the form of images, sounds and actions, and not in the form of text, then in traditional technologies, teaches students to be more active, more attentive and curious in classes, since each information that is recommended is carried out through their participation and action. In the educational system, multimedia technologies are a tool that positively and effectively affects students by combining theoretical, practical, visual, informative, training and control parts. In addition, the use of multimedia training courses in the educational system makes it possible to create high-quality video recordings of demonstrations of theoretical materials, virtual laboratory works and practices, animated models of imitation of various processes, for which it will be necessary to organize practical activities of students in educational classes, computer classes, in the room of technical means of teaching, in addition to the fact that all multimedia training courses used in the educational system have passed practical application and experience, they must also have their own pedagogical characteristics. The pedagogical and psychological characteristics of multimedia training courses will depend on the form and appearance of the description and expression of educational materials used to form knowledge and skills. They should be focused not only on the process of solving examples and issues, performing practical and laboratory classes, but also on the formation of students' knowledge, skills and abilities in the entire educational process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of "multimedia lessons" makes it possible to improve the quality and efficiency of the educational process. In this process, the teacher must visually present the educational material, be able to quickly deliver new material and control the speed and volume of information using animation.

To facilitate the study of materials on natural sciences, educational materials are divided into adjacent parts, and then tasks are planned to be performed sequentially to increase the effectiveness of learning. At the same time, the monitor shows the general view of the school in an interesting way, the blooming of flowers around the school, the words "Welcome" written on the desk, children carrying their bags to school on the screen.

It is important that the educational materials studied using this technology are based on multimedia. The rapid development of science, technology and the industrial sphere raise the

quality of education in all educational institutions to a new level in terms of content, especially in “... improving the quality of education”.

Today, different methods are used to improve and develop each area, as well as different methods are used in the field of education. Therefore, when conducting natural science lessons, it is advisable to use the methods of didactic game technologies, since the variety of methods used in natural science classes increases student's interest in science. The uniqueness of didactic game, unlike traditional education, requires the cooperation of primary school students to organize educational activities, without prohibiting their independence and educational activities.

Consciously directing them into their activities is designed to increase students' interest in learning the basics of science through effective organization, rather than carrying out any kind of team activity, and also provide them with the right to free choice, without limiting the possibilities of individual needs and interests. When conducting such lessons, the teacher must first of all work creatively [4].

Based on the long-term experience and observations of methodologists, it is noted that didactic games are one of the most convenient and effective ways to make science lessons and extracurricular activities meaningful, including other subjects. It is shown that the use of didactic games in the classroom increases the interest of students, skills and abilities aimed at deep acquisition of knowledge.

Also, in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, the need to use a number of innovative technologies in natural science lessons, including role-playing games, clusters, games of entrepreneurs, etc., increases. Preparation for school includes areas of mental and special training of the child. He thought about his ability to complete the tasks set. Tolipova and Numanova noted that modern educational technologies can be used to implement all the tasks included in the system of continuing education of an independent type. The ways of using the module are shown [5].

Many scientists understand the object of education as the purpose, content, laws, methods and principles of the educational process. The improvement of the education system can be considered as an innovative process of introducing modern pedagogical technologies. Here, by innovation, we mean an approach that is implemented to improve the performance of students of a certain class and is accepted by the subject of this innovation as a new one.

Conclusion. Didactic game lessons used in elementary school science have the following advantages:

- students are preparing for didactic game lessons with great interest, as a result of which the effectiveness of obtaining new knowledge is high;

- didactic game lessons are important for elementary school students to test their strength, knowledge, talent when choosing a profession for the first time, as well as to prepare them for life.

Subjects included in the curriculum of educational directions of all educational institutions in our country, textbooks provide an opportunity for students in the educational process to systematically obtain information about our scientific heritage, the rich history of Uzbek people.

This has a positive impact on the hearts and minds of the youth, embodying in them a system of beautiful and vital ideas, as well as self-awareness in their thinking, commitment to historical memory, preservation of sacred values, a sense of patriotism.

When we look at history, it is natural that such processes, achievements of our ancestors evoke a sense of national pride in every future generation. Educational literature is superficial,

one-sided, sometimes misunderstood in the history of physics, mathematics, chemistry, astronomy. This is an indication of the importance of our national spiritual heritage. In order to ensure the active participation of the students in this process, the use of technologies "round table", "discussion", "cluster" (networking), "working in small groups" on topics related to historical sciences is well-effective. The comprehensive explanation of the strategy of independent development of Uzbekistan, the goals and provisions of the people of Uzbekistan for the restoration of the Great State, the essence of our national history to the general public, the Re-study and implementation of our national spiritual heritage is one of the urgent tasks facing every science teacher. The integration of the national historical heritage into the hearts and minds of the students is due to the fact that it covers all spheres of the life of society, the rational use of effective methods and means of propaganda in education. The integration of our national history into the hearts and minds of the youth is carried out through various forms of education and training. This provides for the following tasks:

- to create a differentiated pedagogical and psychological program in educational institutions on the basis of multimedia tools in accordance with the age of students;

- to take into account the psychological characteristics of the students-young people in order to improve the effectiveness of the lesson;

- to work continuously on the formation of lessons on the basis of modern pedagogical and information technologies;

- to develop the methods of presentation of historical sciences in educational programs, textbooks and manuals;

- to deepen the spiritual knowledge of pedagogical personnel, etc.

In educational institutions, it is necessary to prepare students for teaching and training in lessons and extracurricular activities, to print historicity and succession in the organization of reading and teaching, and to base the print of the unit of theory and practice. The analysis of educational programs in the direction of Natural Sciences shows that by organizing the educational process on the basis of the print of historicity, there are not enough specific developments and methodological recommendations on the timing of spiritual education of students.

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